

Surface water from gravity is the fuel of the cell

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An acid-base battery is able to produce electrical current by manipulating the redox balance between water and molecular oxygen. It does this through the physical removal of hydrogen from the anode compartment, forcing oxygen from the dihydro to the dioxide state with the release of electrons (Weng, 2019).

The biological cell is also powered from the combustion of hydroxide ions, and just like an acid-base battery it can also remove hydrogen by electrostatic substitution with cations like sodium and potassium, but it also has another tool in its toolbox for exploiting the electrons stored in water: the ionized surface phase of water, that is formed from pressure exerted by gravity.

At surfaces, water forms a thin layer of an electrically polarized solid phase of water, generated from the water pushing against the sides of the container (Pollack, 2013).

This “compressed ice” is favoured at surfaces because it is denser than water, because it has excluded the protons that link the molecular ice sheets together in ice. This effect of gravity on water “auto-ionizes” it into solid hydrated hydroxide, dozens of times more concentrated than pH 14.

Fig. 12.5 *The effect of pressure on ice. The pressure squeezes out protons, which converts the ice to EZ water.*

This surface water is also what powers osmosis, and since gravity enforces the surface phase, it is also the force behind osmosis. Osmosis also results from tipping the redox balance of oxygen from the dihydro to the dioxide state.

The physical removal of hydrogen is achieved by that the surface phase forms by pushing water against surfaces, ejecting the protons away from the surface, leaving a net negative charge at the surface. This negative charge will attract protons to transfer to the other side of the surface, if it happens to be a membrane that is permeable to protons (Zhao, 2009).

Fig. 11.5 Standard osmosis experiment, with exclusion zones and protons distributed asymmetrically around the dividing membrane.

In osmosis, the surface phase in the endosmotic compartment has been impaired by addition of particles, so the sum of the surface phases on both sides of the membrane has a net negative charge on the endosmotic side. The same asymmetry can also be achieved with a pressure gradient, with a net movement of protons to the low pressure compartment.

The exact same breakdown of OH^- that happens in osmosis when the cation providing electrostatic neutrality leaves, can be known to happen if the cation has been substituted for sodium instead of H^+ . The OH^- experiences no difference. This is exploited by the cell that has substituted H^+ for Na^+ at the outside of the cell surface water. The H^+ for the cathode reaction is physically moved down electrical circuits, allowing the cell to harness the electrical current.

The surface phase is not just the fuel of the cell, it also contributes to assembly of the machinery of the cell. Since the surface phase is able to substitute its conjugate cation H⁺ for cations with higher attractive force, such as potassium, cells in the ocean can accumulate the scarce element potassium into concentrations that equals that of sodium in the oceans (Matveev, 2016).

References

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